

FUNCTIONAL DISORDERS OF THE DIGESTIVE SYSTEM IN CHILDREN: DEFINITION, CLASSIFICATION AND DIAGNOSTIC CRITERIA (LITERATURE REVIEW)

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Abstract. *The Rome criteria were revised in 2016, and clinical guidelines for the diagnosis and treatment of functional gastrointestinal disorders in children were developed in the Russian Federation on their basis. They summarized foreign guidelines and their own experience, proposing tactics for pediatricians in everyday practice. They discuss functional disorders accompanied by abdominal pain: functional nausea and vomiting, functional dyspepsia, irritable bowel syndrome, functional abdominal pain. The definitions, classification, and diagnostic criteria for functional dyspepsia and irritable bowel syndrome have been clarified from the standpoint of modern concepts. Diagnoses of functional gastrointestinal disorders are not always established in pediatric practice, which is why detailed information about these diseases is provided.*

Keywords: *children, functional disorders, functional dyspepsia, functional abdominal pain, irritable bowel syndrome.*

Annotatsiya. *2016 - yilda Rim mezonlari qayta ko'rib chiqildi; ular asosida Rossiya Federatsiyasida bolalarda ovqat hazm qilish organlarining funksional buzilishlarini tashxislash va davolash bo'yicha klinik tavsiyalar ishlab chiqildi; ular xorijiy tavsiyalar va ularning tajribasini umumlashtirdilar, ularning harakatlarining taktikasini taklif qildilar. kundalik amaliyotda pediatr. Ular qorin og'rig'i bilan kechadigan funksional buzilishlarni muhokama qiladilar: funksional ko'ngil aynish va qusish, funksional dispepsiya, irritable ichak sindromi, funksional qorin og'rig'i. Funksional dispepsiya va irritable ichak sindromining ta'riflari, tasnifi va diagnostika mezonlari zamonaviy tushunchalar nuqtai nazaridan aniqlangan. Ovqat hazm qilish tizimining funksional buzilishlarining diagnostikasi pediatriya amaliyotida har doim ham o'rnatilmaydi va shuning uchun ushbu kasalliklar haqida batafsil ma'lumot taqdim etiladi. Ovqat hazm qilish tizimining funksional buzilishlarining diagnostikasi pediatriya amaliyotida har doim ham o'rnatilmaydi va shuning uchun ushbu kasalliklar haqida batafsil ma'lumot taqdim etiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *bolalar, funksional buzilishlar, funksional dispepsiya, funksional qorin og'rig'i, irritable ichak sindromi. bolalar, funksional buzilishlar, funksional dispepsiya, funksional qorin og'rig'i, irritable ichak sindromi.*

Аннотация. *Римские критерии были пересмотрены в 2016 году, на их основе в Российской Федерации разработаны клинические рекомендации по диагностике и лечению функциональных расстройств органов пищеварения у детей, обобщившие зарубежные рекомендации и их опыт, предложившие тактику действий врача-педиатра в повседневной практике. В них рассматриваются функциональные расстройства, сопровождающиеся болью в животе: функциональная тошнота и рвота, функциональная диспепсия, синдром раздраженного кишечника, функциональная абдоминальная боль. Определения, классификация и диагностические критерии функциональной диспепсии и синдрома раздраженного кишечника уточнены с позиций современных представлений.*

Диагнозы функциональных расстройств органов пищеварения не всегда устоялись в педиатрической практике, в связи с чем представлена подробная информация об этих заболеваниях.

Ключевые слова: *дети, функциональные расстройства, функциональная диспепсия, функциональная абдоминальная боль, синдром раздраженного кишечника*

Functional gastrointestinal disorders (FGD) are a complex of constant or recurring symptoms characteristic of a certain age, unexplained by structural and biochemical disorders. According to the IV Rome criteria, functional gastrointestinal diseases in children and adolescents are classified as:

Classification of functional disorders according to the Rome criteria (2016).

H1. Functional disorders associated with nausea and vomiting

- H1a. Cyclic vomiting syndrome
- H1b. Functional nausea and functional vomiting
- H1c. Rumination syndrome
- H1d. Aerophagia

H2. Functional abdominal pain disorders

- H2a. Functional dyspepsia
- H2b. Irritable bowel syndrome
- H2c. Abdominal migraine
- H2d. Functional abdominal pain - not otherwise specified

H3. Functional defecation disorders

- H3a. Functional constipation
- H3b. Fecal incontinence without retention [1,2].

Functional disorders usually do not affect the normal development of the child and may arise as a result of inadequate adaptation in response to external or internal stimuli. Approximately 20–30% of children in the first year of life and 12–20% of older children suffer from functional disorders of the digestive organs [3].

Mechanisms for the development of functional disorders of the digestive organs.

According to modern concepts, functional disorders of the digestive organs generally combine pathophysiological mechanisms and psychosocial factors [4,5].

1. Pathophysiological mechanisms

➤ *Gastrointestinal motility disorders are characteristic of most functional disorders of the digestive system, but are not constant and vary significantly, despite the similarity of symptoms in different patients. This variability can be explained not so much by motility disorders as such (due to underdevelopment of nerve ganglia or disorders of the smooth muscles of the gastrointestinal tract), but by a disorder of neuroendocrine regulation, which depends on many external and internal factors: diet, microbial metabolites, CNS signals.*

➤ *Visceral sensitivity disorders are characteristic of some types of functional disorders of the digestive system (functional dyspepsia, irritable bowel syndrome, infantile intestinal colic). Visceral hypersensitivity can be a consequence of chronic inflammation and impaired neuroendocrine regulation of the gastrointestinal tract.*

➤ *Food intolerance: many patients with different types of functional gastrointestinal disorders are characterized by individual hypersensitivity to certain foods.*

➤ This may be intolerance to certain carbohydrates (fructans, monosaccharides, polyols, lactose), gluten, dietary fiber, fatty and fried foods, as well as abundant foods.

➤ *Intestinal microbiota disorders* have been found in most functional gastrointestinal disorders both in early and late ages. As is known, the intestinal microbiota performs a number of important functions: metabolic, protective, immunogenic. When its composition changes, the spectrum of microbial metabolites may also change. A number of studies have shown a decrease in the level of short-chain fatty acids, in particular butyrate, which has an anti-inflammatory, regenerative effect on the intestinal mucosa and, conversely, an increase in the number of potentially toxic metabolites that can irritate the receptors of the colon and increase pain.

When microbial metabolism is impaired, gases such as hydrogen, methane, carbon dioxide and hydrogen sulfide may be formed in excess. As a result, typical symptoms occur. Impaired microbial metabolism can explain why patients with functional gastrointestinal disorders cannot tolerate various foods, since the range of final metabolites depends on the original product on the one hand and on the composition of the intestinal microbiota on the other.

➤ *Chronic inflammation:* despite the absence of obvious endoscopic changes in the gastric or colonic mucosa, most patients with functional dyspepsia or irritable bowel syndrome show signs of chronic inflammation of the mucosa at the microscopic level, including an increase in the number of mast cells and T-lymphocytes, as well as an increase in the level of proinflammatory cytokines: IL-1 β , IL-6, IL-8, TNF- α and a decrease in the IL-10/IL-12 ratio. This is accompanied by increased permeability of the intestinal barrier, which can also be caused by inflammation. The receptor for neuropeptide S-1, located on the intestinal epithelium, is expressed during inflammation. The gene of this receptor regulates epithelial permeability. This may explain the connection between mild inflammation, increased permeability and impaired motility in functional disorders of the digestive organs (7,8).

The connection between inflammation and motility is also carried out at the level of interaction between the immune and nervous systems of the intestine, and this connection is bidirectional. Lymphocytes of the lamina propria have a number of neuropeptide receptors (SP, CGRP, VIP, SOM, etc.). When immune cells release active molecules and mediators (prostanoids, cytokines) during inflammation, enteric neurons express receptors for these immune mediators (cytokines, histamine, PARS, etc.). Perhaps this also explains the increased visceral sensitivity characteristic of a number of functional disorders of the digestive organs (4,5,6).

2. Psychosocial factors

Symptoms of functional disorders of the digestive organs may appear or become fixed due to disorders of the central nervous system. Stressful situations, long periods of negative psychological impact can lead to the formation of visceral hypersensitivity and impaired motility.

Disruption of the brain-gut axis: due to the common structure and functioning of the central and enteric nervous systems, the gastrointestinal tract responds to central impulses, primarily through the serotonergic system. Hyperproduction of serotonin is a response and compensatory reaction to the activation of 5HT₃ receptors of enterochromaffin cells by catecholamines. At the same time, increased serotonin production and an increase in the level of intracellular calcium are noted, which can cause an increase in pain syndrome with stimulation of peristalsis and the development of visceral hypersensitivity. Long-term persistence of the phenomenon of visceral hypersensitivity in combination with increased activity of the serotonergic system can lead to changes in emotional behavior, psychological status of patients, and the development of depressive states.

Thus, the brain-gut connection is bidirectional. On the one hand, the flow of pain and other impulses coming from the gastrointestinal tract to the brain is fixed in the form of excitation foci, which was confirmed by positron emission tomography data. On the other hand, the counter flow of signals from the central nervous system to the gastrointestinal tract causes and fixes motility disorders and hypersensitivity in a kind of «vicious circle».

The formation of the digestive and motor function of the gastrointestinal tract, the establishment of the intestinal biocenosis, the intestinal immune system, as well as the maturation of the central and enteric nervous system occur in the first months of a child's life. Therefore, any disturbances in the specified period associated with dietary, infectious, stressful influences lead to a disruption of adaptation and dissynchronization of this complex interaction. The interaction of the main mechanisms is considered as the microbiome-gut-brain axis. Disturbances in the formation of intestinal microbiota underlie changes in the spectrum of microbial metabolites, immune disorders, the development of inflammation in the intestine, increased permeability of the intestinal barrier, motor disorders of the gastrointestinal tract, as well as increased excitability and restlessness of the child, forming a symptom complex of functional disorders of the digestive organs, characteristic of young children. The main feature of most functional disorders of the digestive organs at an early age (infant regurgitation, colic, diarrhea) is their favorable course, reduction and disappearance with age as the child matures and adapts (9).

Older children are characterized by functional disorders accompanied by abdominal pain, of which the most common are:

H2. Functional disorders with abdominal pain

H2a. Functional dyspepsia

Must include 1 or more criteria, lasting at least 4 days per month, for at least 2 months:

1. Postprandial heaviness (feeling of fullness in the epigastric region and early satiety).
2. Early satiety.
3. Epigastric pain or heartburn not associated with defecation.
4. After appropriate medical examination, the symptoms cannot be attributed to other diseases.

Subtypes of functional dyspepsia

1. Postprandial distress syndrome: bothersome postprandial heaviness/early satiety.

Additional features: bloating in the upper abdomen; postprandial nausea; frequent belching.

2. Epigastric pain syndrome includes all of the following symptoms:

pain that interferes with a person's normal life activity, or a burning sensation in the epigastrium;

pain is localized in other areas of the abdomen or chest;

pain does not decrease after defecation or gas passage.

Additional symptoms may include:

burning pain, but without a retrosternal component;

pain caused or relieved by eating, but may also occur on an empty stomach.

Functional dyspepsia

1. Definition

1.1. Functional dyspepsia (ICD-X K30) is a symptom complex, pain in the epigastric and/or periumbilical region in combination with 1 or more symptoms: a feeling of fullness in the abdomen

after eating; early satiety; nausea; in the absence of organic, systemic or metabolic diseases that could explain these manifestations [11].

1.2. Only the frequency, periodicity and duration of symptoms allow us to diagnose a functional disorder of the digestive organs, in particular functional dyspepsia (once a week, for at least 2 months in a row) [2, 8].

4. Etiology and pathogenesis

4.1. In the development of functional dyspepsia, as in other forms of functional disorders of the digestive organs manifested by

abdominal pain, factors that disrupt motility and regulation in the brain-gastrointestinal tract axis system play a role, causing visceral hypersensitivity, disruption of mucosal homeostasis, and genetic predisposition also plays a role [2, 6, 12].

4.2. Etiological factors of functional dyspepsia are social maladjustment, psychological stress, fatigue, disruption of sleep, study and rest [14, 15].

4.3. Factors that disrupt mucosal homeostasis include taking medications (anti-inflammatory, antibiotics), food allergies, *Helicobacter pylori* infection [10].

4.4. About 20% of cases of functional dyspepsia develop as a result of acute intestinal infections and food poisoning [11].

4.5. Disorders of the motility of the gastroduodenal zone take part in the genesis of the symptoms of functional dyspepsia: gastroesophageal and duodenogastric reflux, impaired gastric accommodation, slow evacuation from the stomach and duodenum.

Inflammation of the mucous membrane of the stomach and/or duodenum of minimal activity is possible with functional dyspepsia and does not contradict this diagnosis. As a result of a complex of mechanisms, visceral hypersensitivity of the walls of the stomach and duodenum is formed, which leads to the occurrence and persistence of symptoms under the influence of any stimuli [6].

4.6. Functional dyspepsia can act as a gastroenterological «mask» of the syndrome of vegetative dysfunctions separately or in combination with manifestations of dysfunction of other parts of the digestive system or other body systems.

4.7. One of the possible mechanisms for the development of functional dyspepsia is a violation of the secretion of the humoral regulator of the digestive organs, ghrelin, a peptide synthesized by enteroendocrine cells, which activates the motor activity of the stomach and duodenum, gastric secretion, and also causes a feeling of hunger, stimulating appetite through a direct effect on the central nervous system [9]. In addition, changes in the level of gastrin and cholecystokinin may be important in the development of motor disorders in functional dyspepsia.

4.8. *H. pylori* infection may play a certain role in the development of dyspepsia symptoms, contributing to a change in gastric secretion and an increase in visceral hypersensitivity. However, there is no evidence that *H. pylori*-associated gastritis causes dyspeptic symptoms [10].

5. Diagnostics

5.1. Functional dyspepsia is a clinical and anamnestic diagnosis. These clinical signs should be severe enough

to affect the patient's daily activities, i.e. «cause anxiety» [2, 18].

5.2. After a complete examination, it should be clarified that the symptoms cannot be explained by other pathological conditions [2].

5.3. The presence of at least one of the following anxiety symptoms in children requires a more in-depth diagnostic search:

- 1) a family history of inflammatory bowel disease, celiac disease or peptic ulcer disease;
- 2) dysphagia, odynophagia;
- 3) recurrent vomiting;
- 4) signs of gastrointestinal bleeding;
- 5) arthritis;
- 6) unexplained weight loss;
- 7) slow linear growth;
- 8) delayed puberty;
- 9) unexplained fever [2];
- 10) signs of inflammation in the blood (leukocytosis, increased ESR) [14];
- 11) symptoms of anxiety should also include ineffectiveness of standard therapy for the <<functional disorder>> for 2 weeks.

6. Laboratory and instrumental examination methods

6.1. Mandatory examination methods for children with functional dyspepsia include a complete blood count, urine analysis; ultrasound examination of the abdominal cavity (allows you to clarify the condition of the liver, gallbladder, pancreas, and exclude surgical pathology).

6.2. Second-line diagnostic methods include blood chemistry (C-reactive protein, serum iron), fecal immunochemical test, stool analysis for lamblia cysts/fecal PCR for lamblia antigens, pelvic ultrasound (teenage girls), and lactulose breath test.

6.3. Esophagogastroduodenoscopy should be performed in a differentiated manner; this study does not allow for a reliable assessment of the presence of chronic gastritis and its form. Chronic gastritis is a morphological diagnosis, and gastric mucosal biopsy is extremely rarely performed in children in general clinical practice. Overdiagnosis of gastritis contributes to polypharmacy, making it difficult to identify the true cause of dyspepsia [2].

Domestic authors propose the following algorithm for determining indications for esophagogastroduodenoscopy: epidemiological (male gender, adolescence, family history burdened with peptic ulcer disease);

- clinical (night pain, hunger pain, rare severe pain);
- ineffectiveness of standard therapy for 2 weeks.

6.4. In addition, it is obvious that esophagogastroduodenoscopy should be performed if the child has symptoms of <<anxiety>> [2].

6.5. Examination for the purpose of detecting *H. Pylori* in children with functional dyspepsia is indicated if, upon detection of the pathogen, eradication therapy is justified (heredity burdened with peptic ulcer disease, gastric cancer, refractory iron deficiency anemia, idiopathic thrombocytopenic purpura, the patient's desire).

Irritable Bowel Syndrome

H2b. Irritable Bowel Syndrome

1. Abdominal pain lasting at least 4 days per month, associated with one or more of the following:

pain relief after defecation; change in stool frequency; change in stool form.

2. In children with IBS, pain does not resolve after constipation resolves (children in whom pain resolves have functional constipation, not IBS).

3. After appropriate medical evaluation, symptoms cannot be attributed to other diseases

IBS subtypes:

Warning symptoms in children with chronic abdominal pain: family history of inflammatory bowel disease (IBD), celiac disease, or peptic ulcer disease (PUD); persistent pain in the right upper or right lower quadrants of the abdomen; dysphagia, odynophagia; persistent vomiting; gastric or intestinal bleeding; nocturnal diarrhea; arthritis; perianal disease; unmotivated weight loss; growth and sexual development disorders; unexplained fever.

The main principles of constipation treatment include active physical activity, fluid and dietary fiber intake according to physiological norms, and drug therapy.

Definition. Irritable bowel syndrome (ICD-10 K58) is a symptom complex characterized by abnormal stool frequency (4 times a day or more or 2 times a week or less), abnormal stool shape and consistency (segmented/hard or loose/watery), abnormal bowel movements (additional effort, urgency), presence of mucus and bloating in the stool [12,13]. Mandatory conditions for the diagnosis of irritable bowel syndrome are the connection of these symptoms, primarily abdominal pain, with the act of defecation: improvement in condition after defecation, connection of pain with changes in the frequency or consistency of stool.

Epidemiology. The prevalence of irritable bowel syndrome varies from 10 to 25% depending on the region of the world [29,30]. Irritable bowel syndrome can be called a disease of young and middle age, since among patients, people under 50 years of age predominate [18, 19,20,21]. In childhood, irritable bowel syndrome occurs in 1/4 of children under 6 years of age with functional disorders of the digestive organs, occurring with abdominal pain. As a rule, in this age group, irritable bowel syndrome develops as a result of acute intestinal infections. The increase in the incidence of irritable bowel syndrome also occurs in adolescence [14,16,17]

Classification

Depending on the proportion of time during which stool changes of one nature or another (constipation or diarrhea) are observed, irritable bowel syndrome is divided into the following variants:

- A. Irritable bowel syndrome with constipation (IBS-C, IBS-C),
- B. Irritable bowel syndrome with diarrhea (IBS-D, IBS-D),
- C. Mixed irritable bowel syndrome (IBS-M, IBS-M).

Functional abdominal pain

1. Definition

1.1. Functional abdominal pain without other specific manifestations (FAB, FAP-NOS) (ICD-X R10) is a prolonged or frequently recurring pain localized in the periumbilical region or in other areas of the abdomen, observed for more than 2 months, with a partial or complete lack of connection between the pain and physiological events (eating, defecation, etc.), accompanied by a slight loss of daily activity, the absence of organic causes of pain and diagnostic signs of other functional gastrointestinal disorders [15].

1.2. The intensity, nature of pain, frequency of attacks are varied.

2. Epidemiology

2.1. The prevalence of this symptom complex among the adult population, according to various sources, is 0.5–2%, women are more often affected [4].

2.3. Functional abdominal pain without other specific manifestations is observed in school-age children in 2.7% of cases in Colombia, 4.4% in Sri Lanka, 1.2% in the USA and 2% in Germany.

2.4. In Russia, functional abdominal pain accounts for 40% of the pain syndrome in children, mainly in preschool and primary school children [1].

3. Classification

Not developed.

4. Etiology and pathogenesis

4.1. The phenomenon of pain in functional abdominal pain without other specific manifestations is due to increased perception of it in the cerebral cortex due to excessive ascending afferent impulses (to a lesser extent) and its insufficient descending suppression (to a greater extent) [15].

4.2. The process of amplification of pain sensations in functional abdominal pain without other specific manifestations is facilitated by a number of factors, which primarily include mental stress [15]. There is evidence of a link between psychological stress and chronic abdominal pain in childhood and adolescence. Chronic abdominal pain is associated with stressful life situations, such as parental divorce, hospitalization, fears, abuse, problems at school.

4.4. Patients with functional abdominal pain without other specific manifestations often have depression and increased anxiety.

4.5. Visceral hypersensitivity and a relationship with the nature of nutrition, past food poisoning are absent in the pathogenesis of functional abdominal pain without other specific manifestations [15].

5. Diagnostics

To diagnose functional abdominal pain, the following criteria must be met:

- episodic or prolonged abdominal pain, mainly in the periumbilical area, which is not associated with physiological causes (eating, defecation, menstruation); the criteria are not enough to establish a diagnosis of irritable bowel syndrome, functional dyspepsia or abdominal migraine; after a complete examination, it is clarified that the symptoms cannot be explained by anatomical, structural, inflammatory or metabolic causes;
- before making a diagnosis, the symptoms must bother for at least 2 months at least once a week.

6. Laboratory and instrumental examination

6.1. First-line examinations:

- general blood and urine tests;
- coprogram, including examination for helminthiasis and protozoa;
- ultrasound examination of the liver, gallbladder, pancreas, kidneys, pelvic organs.

The presence of anxiety symptoms requires an in-depth diagnostic search (see the section <<Functional dyspepsia>>) [7].

6.2. Second-line examinations (if pain syndrome therapy is ineffective for 2 weeks).

- enzyme immunoassay of blood to detect helminths and lamblia/PCR of feces for lamblia antigens;
- blood test for C-reactive protein, alanine and aspartate aminotransferase, bilirubin, cholesterol, gamma-glutamyl transpeptidase, amylase, lipase;
- analysis of the level of calprotectin in feces;
- computed tomography, magnetic resonance imaging;
- electroencephalography;
- esophagogastroduodenoscopy, colonoscopy;
- Doppler ultrasonography of abdominal vessels (to exclude stenosis of the celiac trunk);

- diagnostic laparoscopy; - gastrointestinal tract X-ray with barium; - consultation with a neurologist, psychiatrist, psychologist, surgeon; - consultation with a gynecologist with examination according to the profile.

7. Differential diagnosis

Since functional abdominal pain has no visible connection with physiological processes (eating, defecation, menstruation) and is not accompanied by other gastrointestinal symptoms indicating damage to the gastrointestinal tract, the diagnostic search is quite broad and covers, in addition to diseases of the digestive system, diseases of the genitourinary, nervous, musculoskeletal and immune systems:

- diseases of the urinary system;
- constipation and its complications;
- gastroesophageal reflux disease;
- inflammatory bowel disease;
- side effects of drugs;
- algomenorrhea, other gynecological pathology;
- diseases of the heart and blood vessels;
- hernias, including intervertebral;
- chronic hepatitis;
- psychogenic causes of pain;
- tumors of the abdominal cavity, brain and spinal cord;
- vegetative-visceral syndrome in neurological diseases;
- metabolic disorders (porphyria, periodic disease).

Thus, FROP in children is a serious problem, causing a high number of visits to pediatricians, gastroenterologists and family doctors. Knowledge of the modern classification, diagnostics and principles of treatment of this pathology will allow doctors to conduct timely diagnostics and treatment.

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